

Radiofrequency measuring receiver with spectrum analyzer function as a tool for noise measurement of semiconductor structures

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Abstract—The article describes the measurement apparatus consisting of a measuring radio frequency receiver working as a spectrum analyzer and specially made amplifiers with very low input noise for the measurement of broadband electrical noise in new semiconductor structures made of two-dimensional lattices of covalent- and metal-organic frameworks, belonging to the Dirac family of materials, intended for the construction of the Quantum Hall resistance standard. The measuring setup operates in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 100 MHz. It is mainly used to detect the cross-frequency appearing at the intersection of the frequency characteristics of the $1/f$ noise and the thermal white noise. The amplifiers have an equivalent voltage input noise of $1 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ and improve the noise factor of the receiver five times, allowing for achieving a noise figure of 0.35 dB for the entire measuring stand.

Keywords—broadband noise, EMC receiver, ULNA, 2D-COF/MOF, QHRS

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrical noise is an unwanted signal that occurs in the elements of the electronic system, limiting the minimum value of the useful signal at the output of the system. Noise can be generated as a result of external disturbances as well as generated internally. Fig. 1 shows the spectrum of the electromagnetic field occurring at the measurement stations in

Fig. 1. The spectrum of the electromagnetic field occurring at the measurement stations in GUM includes several useful frequency bands that are treated as a source of unwanted signal noise.

the Polish National Metrology Institute (NMI) named Central Office of Measures (Główny Urząd Miar in Polish, or GUM). This spectrum, measured with a radio receiver

This project 20FUN03 COMET “Two dimensional lattices of covalent- and metal-organic frameworks for the Quantum Hall resistance standard” has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Funder ID: 10.13039/100014132

designed for electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) testing, contains several helpful frequency bands: radio broadcasting, television, and mobile telephony, important in human activity, but for the instrument on the measuring stand they are a source of unwanted signal, i.e. noise.

The noise generated inside the electronic system is thermal noise related to the chaotic thermal movement of electrons in the resistance of the system, usually with a constant power spectral density as a function of frequency, shot noise related to the current flow, and flicker noise related to the generation and recombination of carriers in semiconductor elements, with a $1/f$ power spectral density.

GUM has quantum standards of voltage and resistance and participates in projects related to their development, including the international European Association of NMIs (EURAMET) activity of the European Metrology Program for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) 20FUN03 COMET project called “Two dimensional lattices of covalent- and metal-organic frameworks (2D-COF/MOF) for the Quantum Hall resistance standard (QHRS)”, the main goal of which is to create QHRS models based on these semiconductor structures that are very attractive in chemical and physical terms [1,2], belonging to the family of Dirac materials [3].

II. COMPONENTS OF THE MEASURING STAGE

Pattern models made of new semiconductor materials are subjected to various tests. The measurement of electrical noise is quite important here because, in the case of too much noise, it will not be possible to build an electrical quantity standard with sufficient precision. In addition to the title measuring radio receiver working as a spectrum analyzer, an essential element of the described measuring system is an ultra-low-noise amplifier (ULNA) working as an input component directly connected to the tested semiconductor structure, and therefore the impedance matching and the quality of its first-stage noise parameters are the most important. To be able to measure the noise of new semiconductor structures, the first amplification stage should have a noise level as low as possible compared to the expected noise of the tested structure.

A. ULNA

Due to the bandwidth of the transmitted frequencies, at least three types of such ULNA amplifiers can be distinguished. Narrowband ULNA is designed for measurements in a strictly defined frequency. The need for the usage of such an amplifier was presented at an earlier EMC EUROPE conference when discussing power measurements in the terahertz band with the use of electromagnetic wave

beats [4] and an example of such a measurement system is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. An exemplary system for measuring the power of electromagnetic wave sources in the T-band with the use of a narrow-band ULNA amplifier.

The second type of amplifier is intended for testing low-frequency noise, most often up to 10 kHz, where there are the highest noise power values, mainly associated with $1/f$ pink noise, and here correlation methods are used to eliminate noise inside the instruments. Two measuring tracks are used here. Thanks to the relatively low frequency, it is possible to digitize the signal simultaneously in both measurement paths. Next, a fast Fourier transform (FFT) is applied and the values of the processed signals are fed into the mathematical cross-correlation procedure. An example of such a solution is described in the publication [5, 6, 7] and its simplified block diagram can look like in Fig.3.

Fig. 3. Block diagram of an example measurement of electrical noise of a semiconductor structure with the use of the correlation method to eliminate the noise of the measuring device.

On the other hand, broadband noise is studied because it is essential to find the cross-frequency where $1/f$ noise is equal to thermal white noise. Finding this point on the frequency response is important due to the design of the target apparatus using the quantum standards built of new materials. It is difficult to predict where this characteristic point may appear on the frequency response because different semiconductors show different cross-frequencies from a few hundred hertz to even hundreds of megahertz.

In the 20FUN03 COMET project, there is also a task to adapt the apparatus to measure the noise of model semiconductor structures with the greatest possible precision. At GUM, it was decided to prepare apparatus whose task is to measure broadband noise in the range from 10 kHz to 100 MHz and to detect the cross-frequency for a given semiconductor structure model. It would be difficult to use the correlation method here because it would require the use of analog-to-digital converters with a speed ten thousand times faster than in the method presented above (Fig. 3). In this

situation, the focus was on building a broadband amplifier with good parameters based on components currently available on the market. The criterion for selecting the transistor of the first amplifying stage consisted of two points:

- input noise below $1 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$
- and operating frequency up to at least 100 MHz.

From among a dozen or so transistors, the N-channel FET transistor BF682 was selected, which has a typical noise value at 100 kHz at the level of $0.8 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ and a typical value of the transient frequency f_T at the level of 715 MHz, which is equivalent to the product of gain and bandwidth, hence for the planned maximum amplifier frequency of 100 MHz gives a maximum gain of about $7 \text{ V}/\text{V} \cdot \Omega$

Fig. 4 shows a simple scheme of the first stage of the amplifying ULNA amplifier with a description of the influence of each element present in this circuit on its operation. In the project, the first stage was made based on the BF682 transistor and the gain of this stage is about $4 \text{ V}/\text{V}$.

Fig. 4. The first stage of the ULNA amplifier designed to measure the electrical noise of new semiconductor structures made of 2D-COF/MOF materials with a description of the influence of each amplifier element on its work.

In the second and third stages, an amplifier based on the LM6629 integrated circuit with an input noise voltage of $0.69 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ was used. This amplifier has a -3dB frequency response of 900 MHz and is adapted to work in a 50Ω impedance system, i.e. its input and output impedance is 50Ω . These stages' gain is equal to $10 \text{ V}/\text{V}$. In the last stage, a commercial amplifier HVA-200M-40-F was used, operating

Fig. 5. Individual stages amplifying the noise signal in the version of the maximum amplification of the ULNA amplifier with the shown amplification of individual stages and the equivalent noise voltage values.

in the frequency range from DC to 200 MHz, with a gain of 100 V/V (40 dB) and an input noise voltage of 4.5 nV/√Hz. All stages of the amplifier with noise determination on individual stages are shown in Fig. 5. The ULNA amplifier made in this way has a gain of about 40,000 V/V, which corresponds to about 92 dB, and an equivalent input noise voltage of about 1 nV/√Hz. If a sensitive oscilloscope or spectrum analyzer is used, such a high gain is not required, so the number of stages can be delimited.

The amplifier made in this way works very well in the range of 10 kHz to 30 MHz. Above 30 MHz, the first stage shows fluctuations in the frequency response, for this reason, for more accurate measurements of electrical noise in this frequency range, the super low noise FET transistor CE3512K2 was used, which has a noise figure (NF) equal to 0.30 dB, which means that the input noise should be multiplied by 1.035 next to the amplifier which results from the formula:

$$N_o = N_i \cdot G \cdot 10^{(NF[dB]/20)} [V] \quad (1)$$

where N_o – noise voltage at the output expressed in V, N_i – input noise voltage in V, G – amplifier voltage gain (linear), NF – noise figure in dB.

B. Radiofrequency Measuring Receiver as a Spectrum Analyzer

When reviewing the technical documentation of active semiconductor elements, it can be noticed that many manufacturers use spectrum analyzers in systems to measure the frequency characteristics of electrical noise of these elements.

The project uses the ESCI 3 measuring radio wave receiver visible in the background in Fig. 3. It has a built-in spectrum analyzer function, which is used to measure the noise characteristics of the new semiconductor structures. This receiver measures the power of electrical signals and has a high sensitivity to measure single pW signals coming from the antenna.

The spectrum analyzer built into the receiver measures the amount of electrical power of the input signal in the full frequency range, which is from 9 kHz to 3 GHz. It has a low input impedance suitable for microwave and television measurements. Television systems use 75 Ω and microwave 50 Ω. Here, the input impedance is set to 50 Ω because the final amplification stages of the made UNLA amplifier have an output impedance of 50 Ω. We can set the spectrum analyzer reading to a different unit instead of power, e.g. voltage, but the instrument will convert this voltage from the measured power for 50 Ω impedance. That is, if we connect a voltage source with an impedance other than 50 Ω, the indicated voltage value will not correspond to the real voltage connected to the input. When working at lower frequencies, the principle of impedance matching also applies, hence the ULNA amplifier used in the project must have an output impedance of 50 Ω.

A spectrum analyzer measures the power of electromagnetic signals dissipated across its input resistance. The noise generated on the output resistor of devices connected to the analyzer is transferred to its input. Maximum noise power transfer is when impedance-matched. In this case, two 50 Ω resistors. Each of the two participating resistors dissipates the noise equally in itself and in the other resistor.

The noise value visible on the spectrum analyzer in the absence of other active devices connected to its input does not depend on its input and the added to its input resistances but only on the temperature and set band. Its power, expressed in dBm at room temperature of about 300 K for a given band Δf , is expressed by the formula:

$$P(\text{dBm}) = -174 \text{ dBm} + 10 \log(\Delta f) \quad (2)$$

therefore, for the assumed frequency range of 100 MHz, it gives a noise power value of -166 dBm, which corresponds to about -59 dBμV, and the RMS value of the noise voltage of 1.1 nV (about 7 nV_{p-p}) for the 50 Ω system.

With very precise measurements of low-value electrical noise, the direct use of the ESCI 3 receiver may be impossible due to the rather high NF value, which for this device is about 7 dB. For these reasons, four stages of the ULNA amplifier were used. Two amplification stages were made using the CE3512K2 transistor (T_i) with 0.30 dB NF and 4 V/V gain and two using the LMH 6629 amplifier (A_i) with 8 dB NF and 10 V/V gain. To determine the new NF value for the entire system, Friis's formula and the conversion formulas of NF into noise factor (F) were used, which are presented below to explain the mathematical operations.

The NF and the F are values that indicate the deterioration of the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) caused by components in the signal chain. These values are used to evaluate the performance of an amplifier or radio receiver, with lower values indicating better performance.

The noise factor F of the system is defined as [8]:

$$F = \frac{SNR_i}{SNR_o} \quad (3)$$

where SNR_i and SNR_o are the input and output signal-to-noise ratios, respectively. The SNR values are unitless power factors. The NF is defined in units of decibels (dB) [8]:

$$NF = 10 \log_{10}(F) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{SNR_i}{SNR_o} \right) = SNR_{i, \text{ dB}} - SNR_{o, \text{ dB}} \quad (4)$$

where $SNR_{i, \text{ dB}}$, and $SNR_{o, \text{ dB}}$ are in units (dB).

Friis's formula for calculating the total noise factor of a cascade of stages, each it's the noise factor F_i and power gain G_i [8]:

$$F_{ULNA} = F_1 + \frac{F_2-1}{G_1} + \frac{F_3-1}{G_1 G_2} + \frac{F_4-1}{G_1 G_2 G_3} \quad (5)$$

$$F_{SYSTEM} = F_{ULNA} + \frac{F_{SA}-1}{G_{ULNA}} \quad (6)$$

where F_{SYSTEM} , F_{ULNA} and F_{SA} are the noise factors of the whole circuit of measuring system, the ULNA, and the spectrum analyzer itself, respectively, and G_{ULNA} is the gain of the ULNA.

Based on the above data of the T_i and A_i subassemblies and the quoted calculation formulas, the parameters of various variants of the ULNA amplifier and the parameters of the entire measurement set can be determined. For three-stage

ULNA amplifiers, the following parameters are obtained. For the T1A1A2 set, the weakest measurement performance was obtained, because with the amplification of 484 V/V, the NF for the entire measurement set was about 1.15 dB. For the T1T2A1 set with a gain of 47.4 dB (234 V/V) for the whole measurement system, F was about 1.09 and NF was 0.36 dB. Slightly better parameters were achieved by the four-stage T1T2A1A3 set, which for the amplification above two thousand V/V achieved F equal to 1.08 and NF equal to 0.35 dB, so the noise parameters of the receiver were improved five times.

III. CHECKING ELECTRONIC COMPONENTS AND PREPARING A STAND FOR MEASURING NEW SEMICONDUCTOR STRUCTURES

When measuring electrical noise using a spectrum analyzer in a radio wave measuring receiver, it should be borne in mind that this device applies to a variety of electromagnetic wave measurements. It is a universal device, it has many different settings. The noise measurement result may be different with different selections of filters, detectors, or reading scales. Three different detectors can be used to measure the noise. The RMS detector should be used when reading the noise power value, the Average detector- for the noise voltage value, and the Sample detector in the case of imaging the dispersion of the noise waveform, but the latest has less precision and makes it difficult to prepare the measurement uncertainty balance. When using other detectors, the crest factor (CF) must be taken into account. Typically, CF is between 1 and 2. Accurate results are not obtained here, as CF is precisely calculated only for well-defined waveforms of electrical signals.

To obtain the highest precision of the measurement, use intermediate frequency (IF) filters with the narrowest possible resolution bandwidth (RBW), preferably with a width of 1 or 10 Hz, and a video filter with similar video bandwidth (VBW). When using filters with such narrow bands, the sweep time can be up to several hours. To shorten the sweep time and to use a more accurate, rectangular IF filter overall frequency response, an FFT filter type should be taken.

Checking the spectrum analyzer consists in shorting the input with a 50 Ω terminator. The envelope of the noise waveform should be a straight line. The average value should correspond to the current temperature of the detector. Previously, the analyzer was calibrated for its standard applications.

Each amplifying stage of the ULNA amplifier has a checked frequency response from which the stage gains are determined and the presence of residual 1/f pink noise is checked. If it occurs, corrective values are introduced and this is taken into account in the uncertainty balance. Fig. 6 shows the testing of one of the amplification stages of the ULNA amplifier. The amplifier is short-circuited or a defined noise source is connected. Particularly important is the measurement of the first stage, where there are high input impedances. The short circuit eliminates the noise of high input resistance by reducing thermal white noise, which is important in determining the residual pink noise that is present in any device containing semiconductor components.

The first amplifying stage operating as a trans-impedance amplifier should enable operation with different input

Fig. 6. Checking one of the amplification stages in the ULNA amplifier for the presence of residual 1/f pink noise in the lower part of the frequency characteristic of the measurement setup.

impedance values due to the different impedances of the tested semiconductor structures.

IV. CONCLUSION

The measuring radio frequency receiver is a device of high precision and has many utility functions. Thanks to this, it can be used besides EMC testing for measurements in many metrological severe tasks. Functionality as a spectrum analyzer enables the measurement of broadband electrical noise. In this work, it was tested for noise measurements of semiconductor structures made of Dirac materials and specifically prepared for measuring the noise of two-dimensional lattices of covalent- and metal-organic frameworks of semiconductor structures intended for the construction of a QHRS standard. Due to the application of these structures to the electrical quantity standard, very low noise values should be expected. For these reasons, it is necessary to build a measuring stand with better parameters than the receiver itself, and thus extend this stand with an ULNA amplifier working as a receiver preamplifier. The made amplifier has an input noise voltage equivalent of 1 nV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$, is matched to the receiver's 50 Ω input and can have a maximum voltage gain of 92 dB, which corresponds to 46 dB of power gain. The implemented variant of the ULNA amplifier improves the noise factor of the receiver five times and allows to obtain of a noise figure value at a level of 0.35 dB.

This work proves the usefulness of the EMC receiver in measuring electrical noise using its spectrum analyzer as a modern tool in the search for cross-frequency at the crossover of pink 1/f noise and white noise frequency characteristics if the special construction device like the ULNA is connected at the input of the analyzer.

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